

On the Structure Analysis by X-Ray Diffraction

S. N. BAGCHI

5550 Bellerive, Brossard, Quebec, J4Z 3C8, Canada

The main purpose of this paper is to draw the attention of specialists to the problems of structure analysis by pointing out the limitations of conventional theories and the equivocal nature of the results obtained by the methodologies usually adopted vis-a-vis the advantages of utilising the concepts and results of Unified Kinematic Theory of Diffraction by Matter of *Any Kind*. Since the results obtained by structure analysts are often used by workers in various other fields, it is hoped that these remarks would be helpful to them also.

X-RAY diffraction studies have become an essential tool for obtaining information about the structure of materials. In recent years, dynamic theory of X-ray diffraction is being increasingly used to obtain valuable information about the defects and imperfections of "perfect" crystals. But overwhelming number of substances usually encountered in nature can be dealt with sufficient accuracy by kinematic theories of diffraction. In this paper I shall deal with kinematic theories *only* and that also in the Faunhofer zone. This domain covers the conventional theories of diffraction, namely, Laue-Bragg-Debye-Waller theory of crystals; Zernike-Prins-Debye-Menke theory of liquids and the theory of scattering by amorphous matter as well as the theory of small angle scattering (SAS) proposed by Debye, Warren, Guinier and others.

For various reasons one uses these conventional theories to obtain useful results from X-ray diagrams, though it has been known for more than 30 years that these conventional (ideal) theories fail to explain, (sometimes even qualitatively), many of the peculiar features of diffraction patterns of complicated substances. To overcome these difficulties, specialists had often made many *ad hoc* additional assumptions of mutually contradictory nature and these led to many fruitless controversies, particularly in the field of SAS.

The inadequacies of these conventional theories pointed out the *necessity* of developing a unified kinematic theory of diffraction by matter of *any kind*. During 1952-56, Hosemann and Bagchi developed such a theory. It is now generally recognised that this unified theory is the most comprehensive kinematic theory available at the moment. Optical diffraction patterns of many carefully prepared 2-dimensional models whose structural parameters were known beforehand fully substantiated the results obtained from this theory so that there can be no doubt about the universal validity (*albeit* for kinematic theory) of this theory. It enables one to find not only the domains of validities of the conventional theories, but also their limitations and inadequacies. For example, controversies in SAS were resolved by showing

that in SAS various factors play their roles and each of the proponents of a particular point of view was dealing with systems where other factors (neglected by them) play only minor part. Moreover, this unified theory can extract information about the structure which could not be obtained from any other theory. Of course, for this one needs systematic, careful and often arduous investigations. But the outcome of such painstaking hard work can be rewarding.

Notwithstanding these advantages of the unified theory, in order to get practical results (without raising the question—how far these results are unequivocal or reliable), workers had almost always used the conventional methodologies. In the monograph¹ as well as in various other publications²⁻⁷ the problems of limitations and inadequacies of these standard theories as well as the equivocal (if not entirely wrong) nature of the results obtained from such studies had been discussed critically and quantitatively. One cannot over-emphasise the fact that only this comprehensive theory can lead us to reliable simplifying assumptions often needed in practice. Further, even in cases where the conventional theories are more or less applicable, comprehensive studies of diffraction patterns, if analysed carefully with the help of unified theory, can yield much more detailed information about the structure of the substance investigated which are not possible to obtain from conventional theories.

Outline of the Unified Kinematic Theory of Diffraction* :

Diffraction patterns are primarily governed by the distances between the scattering centres and by their relative fluctuations. In order to decipher the diagrams our first task is to get the intensity function $I(\vec{b})$ from the observed coherently scattered intensity by eliminating all non-essential factors, (namely, factors depending on the experimental arrangement, Lorentz factors, absorption factor,

* For comprehensive discussions and derivations see ref. 1. A useful condensed account emphasising the significant features of the theory is to be found in ref. 2.

“termination effect”, incoherent scattering, etc.), which do not depend on the density function $\rho(\vec{x})$.

The usual expression for $I(\vec{b})$ given by (1), though exact, is practically useless.

$$I(\vec{b}) = \sum_n \sum_m f_m f_n^* \exp -2\pi i [\vec{b} \cdot (\vec{x}_m - \vec{x}_n)] \dots (1)$$

(f_m is the structure amplitude of the m th atom, f_n^* its complex conjugate). For getting useful results one is forced to introduce statistical distribution of scattering centres. It should be noted that even if the structure is statistically homogeneous, the distribution function must be introduced in the density function $\rho(\vec{x})$ in physical space and not in the expression for $I(\vec{b})$ of Fourier space. If one intends to introduce the averaging over all the positions of atoms in expression (1), one has to incorporate the pair-distribution function in (1) and not the density distribution of atoms. Conventional (ideal) theories are obtained by assuming different probability distribution functions for the occurrence of atoms at different positions. Each one is using a particular form of the distribution function suitable for the idealised system which is being treated. All of them are therefore applicable to idealised systems which are statistically homogeneous.

For the comprehensive unified theory we need a more general as well as tractable expression for $I(\vec{b})$ which depends only on the density distribution $\rho(\vec{x})$ and its inverse Fourier transform $Q(\vec{x})$, (sometimes called generalised Patterson function). For any substance whatsoever, they are given by (2) and (3).

$$I(\vec{b}) = \mathfrak{F} \rho(\vec{x}) \cdot \mathfrak{F} \rho(-\vec{x}) \dots (2)$$

$$Q(\vec{x}) = \mathfrak{F}^{-1} I(\vec{b}) = \rho(\vec{x}) * \rho(-\vec{x}) = \int \rho(\vec{y}) \rho(\vec{x} + \vec{y}) d\vec{v} \dots (3)$$

The symbols \mathfrak{F} , \mathfrak{F}^{-1} represent Fourier integral and its inverse ; * denotes convolution product.

For any arbitrary structure we can get the desired density function by solving the nonlinear integral equation (3).

The solution and its application to several model structures had been given^{1,8-10}. It is very sensitive to experimental errors and has not yet been used in practice. Nevertheless, theoretically it showed the limitations of standard method of crystal structure analysis and also gave a solution to the problems of homometric structures¹¹. It should also be noted that the deconvolution of the Q-function leads us directly to the density function which is unique if the substance is bounded and is centrosymmetric. It has a great potentiality for solving problems where conventional theories are powerless⁴.

For arbitrary structures expressions (2) and (3) can offer only a few important results. For example, it proved that the theorem of Ornstein and Zernike, which states that the small angle scattering

is proportional to the fluctuation of the density distribution of the scattering material, is generally correct for the observable part of the intensity function. It revealed that this theorem does not include Debye's volume scattering factor which is always unobservable. It also showed that small angle scattering may arise from “frozen” structures also (and may have nothing to do with the compressibility), if the scattering centres are distributed suitably.

The detailed analysis of (2) and (3), however, led to a very important theoretical conclusion. It showed the necessity of introducing the concept of generalised lattice and yielded the necessary and sufficient conditions for its definition. With the help of the generalised lattice one can obtain a convenient expression of the (average) density function. The expression of the intensity function is then calculated simply from its Fourier transformation. The expression for $I(\vec{b})$ of a statistically homogeneous system then led to the corresponding expressions of the conventional theories under restricted conditions, thus revealing their domains of validities.

In order to express ρ in a convenient form for any arbitrary structure one must generalise the concept of ideal lattice and distinguish between a lattice and aggregates of lattices (clusters) which may form a macro-lattice in which the building blocks are micro-lattices themselves. Biological substances and polymers often form such macro-lattices.

The fact that every substance is finite is taken into account by truncating the lattice with the help of Ewald's shape (or stencil) function $s(\vec{x})$.

(i) *Generalised lattice and its intensity function :*

A generalised lattice need not be a perfectly periodic pattern, but has to distribute the lattice points with a given *a priori* statistics. The statistics of neighbouring lattice points inform us about the degree of distortion of the ideal lattice. The generalised lattice depending on this degree of distortion can represent the structures of not only crystals, liquids and gases or amorphous matter, but also of any statistically homogeneous substance provided one distributes the atoms around the reference lattice points. From the standpoint of diffraction, the distinction between crystals, liquids and amorphous substances lies in the degree of distortion of the ideal lattice. Nature never places the atoms on the exact sites of ideal lattice points. Slightest thermal motion would disperse the atoms around the ideal lattice points. In almost all cases distortions arise from geometric configurations and from anharmonic vibrations of atoms. Consequently, they can be conveniently separated into distortions of the first kind and that of the second kind. The first gives the deviations of centroids of atoms from their most probable positions due to harmonic vibrations around their average positions (lattice points) as well as the effect of different types

of atoms at the lattice points (e.g. mixed crystals). The second type distorts the perfect lattice itself and is mainly responsible for the peculiar characteristic features of diffraction diagrams. It produces the characteristic patterns of the humps of reflexions besides contributing to the background scattering. The first type of distortion, on the other hand, produces a general background scattering without affecting the nature of reflexion-humps and the underlying lattice type. Consequently, a quantitative analysis of the background scattering, almost always neglected by the specialists, is necessary to determine the finer features of the distorted lattice. Sufficient criteria had been established to distinguish between the effects produced by the two types of distortion. Such a systematic comprehensive study of diffraction diagrams are very important for solving many vexed problems of SAS, particularly in the fields of alloys and catalysts.

A generalised lattice is defined as an infinitely extended "point structure" of weight unity with the origin at $\vec{x}=0$ by eq. (4) :

$$z_k(\vec{x}) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(\vec{x} - \vec{x}_k) \quad \dots (4)$$

It must also satisfy the following three conditions :

(a) $\frac{\Delta^2 v}{v} = \frac{\Delta^2 N(v)}{N(v)} = \text{constant for all values of } v \quad \dots (4a)$

v is the volume of the lattice cell obtained by joining the lattice point with its immediate neighbours by nonintersecting vectors. $N(V)$ is the number of atoms (or molecules) in the volume V . Δ^2 is the symbol for square of the fluctuation.

(b) $\Delta^2 v = N \Delta^2 v, (N \gg \gg 1) \quad \dots (4b)$

(c) The relation (4b) means that the volume of every lattice cell fluctuates independently. There is no correlation between cell volumes. The lattice cell themselves, however, are arbitrarily distorted so that their shapes and sizes vary from one cell to another quite arbitrarily. One can therefore describe the generalised lattice with the help of only one normalised a priori statistics of the cell volumes.

$$H(V) = H_{p_1 p_2 p_3}(\vec{x}) \quad \dots (4c)$$

The (average) intensity function of a structure forming a generalised lattice is then given by

$$\bar{I}(\vec{b}) = \overline{N(V)} [|\bar{f}_0|^2 - |D_0|^2 |\bar{f}_0|^2] - \frac{1}{v} [|D_0|^2 |\bar{f}_0|^2 Z * |S|^2] \quad \dots (5)$$

Here,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} S(\vec{b}) &= \sum s(\vec{x}); \\ D_0(\vec{b}) &= \sum A_0(\vec{x}); \\ A_0(\vec{x}) &= A_p(\vec{x}) = \delta(\vec{x} - \vec{x}_p), \\ Z(\vec{b}) &= \sum z(\vec{x}); \\ z(\vec{x}) &= \lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^{\pm M} \sum_{k=1}^{\pm M} \delta(\vec{x} - \vec{x}_m + \vec{x}_k); \\ \bar{\rho}(\vec{x}) &= \bar{\rho}_0 * [z(\vec{x}) * \delta(\vec{x} - \Delta \vec{x}_p)] \cdot s(\vec{x}) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad \dots (6)$$

$z(\vec{x})$ gives the lattice statistics, $\delta(\vec{x})$ is Dirac's delta function and $|S|^2$ is called the shape factor. $\bar{\rho}_0(\vec{x})$ denotes the average density function of a cell element with its centroid lying at the lattice point, $\Delta \vec{x}_p$ gives the deviation of the centroid from that lying at the lattice point \vec{x}_p .

The distance statistics $z(\vec{x})$ of the generalised lattice can then be expressed in terms of the normalised distribution function $H_{p_1 p_2 p_3}(\vec{x})$ for the location of the p th cell whose mean position is given by

$$\vec{x}_p = p_1 \vec{a}_1 + p_2 \vec{a}_2 + p_3 \vec{a}_3 \quad \dots (7)$$

Here p_k 's are integers and \vec{a}_k 's are the average values of the three fundamental lattice vectors.

Thus, we can write

$$z(\vec{x}) = \sum_{p_1=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{p_2=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{p_3=-\infty}^{\infty} H_{p_1 p_2 p_3}(\vec{x}) \quad \dots (8)$$

As noted before, the distinctive and characteristic features of diffraction diagrams are determined mainly by the nature of the function $Z(\vec{b})$. It can then be analysed quantitatively with the help of a few parameters of neighbour statistics which can be obtained from experimental data.

The expression (5) for the intensity function of a generalised lattice degenerates to those of conventional theories for particular cases. For example, if the humps of the shape factor $\Delta |S|^2$ are very much greater in all the directions (symbol $\gg \gg \gg$) than that of the reflexions ΔZ , we get crystalline reflexions. That means, if $\Delta Z(\vec{b} - \vec{b}_n)$ behaves practically as a delta function compared to $\Delta |S|^2(\vec{b} - \vec{b}_n)$, the reflexion located at \vec{b}_n would be of crystalline nature. Thus, the crystalline reflexions whose properties are given by Laue-Bragg theory are produced under the condition

$$\Delta |S|^2(\vec{b} - \vec{b}_n) \gg \gg \Delta Z(\vec{b} - \vec{b}_n) \quad \dots (9)$$

On the otherhand, if

$$\Delta Z(\vec{b} - \vec{b}_n) \gg \gg \Delta |S|^2(\vec{b} - \vec{b}_n) \quad \dots (10)$$

we would get liquid-like reflexions with the properties predicted by Zernike-Prins and Debye-Menke. It should be carefully noted that the expressions for $\bar{I}(\vec{b})$ for the case (10), that means also the expressions for the conventional theories of liquids, do not contain the (000)-reflexion which is always crystalline in nature.

Finally, the domain of amorphous scattering is reached when $Z(\vec{b})$ attains its steady value unity.

$$Z(\vec{b}) = 1 \quad \dots (11)$$

Of course, when none of these conditions are exactly fulfilled we get composite reflexions which do not

satisfy the properties of reflexions given by conventional theories. It should be particularly noted that all these different types of reflexion-humps may be encountered in the diffraction pattern of a *single pure* substance depending on its characteristic $z(\vec{x})$ -function. The humps of reflexions are essentially the humps of $Z(\vec{b})$ -function. The analysis of the expression for the intensity function $I(\vec{b})$ given by eq. (5) for $\vec{b} \rightarrow 0$ revealed many important features of SAS and the roles of various factors like fluctuation of electron density distribution within a particle, polydispersity, density of packing, etc. in determining the nature and character of small angle scattering.

After this short summary of the unified theory we are now in a position to point out the limitations and inadequacies of the methodologies based on conventional theories usually adopted in practice. But due to limitation of space, I shall mention here very briefly the most important aspects of the problems. For details one must consult the literature already cited.

Structure of Crystals :

From the time of Kirchoff till 1952 it had been almost an axiom of physics that from intensity data *alone* one cannot determine directly the density distribution of the scattering substance because the "phases" are lost. To calculate the density distribution one must know the amplitudes and phases of the scattered radiation. Consequently, major efforts of crystallographers had been directed to the determination of phases of reflexions by auxiliary methods. But before 1952, (cf. refs. 8-10), it was not noticed that if one takes only the integrated intensities of reflexions at the reciprocal (ideal) lattice points, (which means, one idealises to infinitely extended perfect crystals), then the electron density distribution calculated from Fourier synthesis, even *when the amplitudes and phases are exactly known*, would no longer be unique. For n reflexions there would be 2^n alternative structures for the centrosymmetric case, all of which would give the same integral intensity at the lattice points, (homomorphs and pseudo-homomorphs^{9,11}). Of course, most of these alternative structures could be discarded if we have sufficient knowledge of the physicochemical properties of the substance investigated. But the example of "bixbyite" (cited by Pauling) showed that one cannot always eliminate *a priori* alternative structures which are equally valid from physicochemical standpoint. For complicated biological structures it is all the more difficult to resolve the possible ambiguities unequivocally. Frog myelin membrane offers a simple but striking example of biological structure⁴.

Now a days various theoretical (mainly statistical) methods have been suggested to determine the phases of crystal reflexions, but none of them can determine them with certainty. Here again myelin membrane gives a concrete example of the ambiguity.

Since practically all the available structures had been determined by guessing correctly(?) the phases of reflexions and by taking integral intensities of reflexions whose maxima were supposed to be located at the ideal lattice points, the possibility of a different structure (pseudo-homometric or homometric) cannot be eliminated even in principle and less so for complicated biological structures. It is therefore rather misleading to call the methodology based upon the standard Fourier synthesis and the theoretical determination of phases as "Direct Method" for the determination of structure. The results obtained by such a methodology can *never* yield the structure of the substance investigated *unequivocally*.

Only methods based upon the solution of the Q-function, (now a days often called generalised Patterson function) can really be called the "Direct Method". It does not depend on a particular theory and for a bounded centrosymmetrical structure it offers the *unique* structure. But for this one must determine the profiles of reflexions as well as the shifts of the maxima from those of the corresponding ideal lattice points, i.e., the gradients of structure factors within the reflexion-hump^{9,10}. Consequently, for ordinary crystals containing many unit cells it would be extremely difficult to apply this method. But for many biological structures containing only a few cells, the analysis of the Q-function seems to be very promising. It can also resolve the ambiguities of phases of reflexions (for details see ref. 4).

Hence, we can assert that the present day methodologies usually employed to determine the structure of crystals do not yield the unequivocal structure sought for. The alternative structures cannot be excluded as long as one pursues the conventional techniques and this is particularly true for complicated biological structures and polymers.

The Structure of Liquids

Liquid-like diffuse reflexions originate from the conditions given by eq. (10). The intensity function in this case does not contain the contribution of (000)-reflexion. Our information about the structure of liquids is usually obtained from the analysis of the radial distribution function (RDF), $4\pi r^2 g(r)$. RDF is calculated from the inverse transform of the intensity function. But the expression for the intensity function for the liquids which are commonly used, (first derived by Zernike and Prins in 1927), is valid for "primitive" liquids, i.e., a liquid which does not contain clusters, (see refs. 1-3). But it had been shown that even simple liquids like argon near the triple point show the presence of micro-clusters. It seems very likely that all liquids near their melting points contain densely packed micro-clusters*. In such cases one can safely use the relevant $I(\vec{b})$. But since it does not contain the (000)-reflexion, if SAS extends to observable region,

* From the standpoint of statistical mechanics, liquids have to be treated as small thermodynamic systems.

as it does in the case of liquids at higher temperatures, particularly near the critical region, the calculated RDF would not be correct.

However, even if we assume that the calculated RDF is correct, we have to deconvolute it to obtain structural information about the density distribution. The usual method of analysis with the help of a few Gaussian functions placed around the humps of RDF diagram can give us only average distances between first two or three neighbours and their coordination numbers. But if we note that $g(r)$ is really a convolution square of the density functions (cf. ref. 1), it would be obvious that the standard method is both *mathematically and physically wrong*, (for the necessary proof see ref. 2). Consequently, the results obtained from such investigations are of questionable value.

The function $g(r)$ is given by

$$g(r) = z(x) - \delta(x-0) = \overline{\overline{g_0(r) + \rho = \rho n_2(r)}} \dots (12)$$

$\overline{\overline{n_2(r)}}$ is the space-time average (symbol $\overline{\overline{\quad}}$), of the so called pair-distribution function. In order to obtain information about the density distribution we have to deconvolute $g(r)$. The problem was discussed in the monograph (ref. 1) but the method described there was valid only for the one dimensional case. It should be carefully noted that deconvolution of spherically symmetrical function cannot be treated as a one dimensional case. Many authors, particularly in the field of biological structures, had committed such errors.

We can get many useful and reliable structural parameters of liquids if we analyse RDF correctly with the help of the unified theory. The method had been described in details⁵ and also applied to many simple liquids^{5,6}. It had been shown that in the case of "primitive" liquids only one spherically symmetric coordination statistics of the first neighbour $H_1(r)$ is enough to calculate the distribution function $H_p(r)$ of the p th neighbour. They are given by, (for derivations see ref. 2),

$$H_1(r) = \frac{1}{(\pi\alpha^2)^{3/2}} \exp[-r^2/\alpha^2] \dots (13)$$

$$H_p(r) = \frac{1}{4\pi^{3/2} m^{1/3} \alpha r_p} \frac{1}{r} \{ \exp[-(r-r_p)^2/m\alpha^2] - \exp[-(r+r_p)^2/m\alpha^2] \} \dots (14)$$

Here r_p denotes the distance of the centroid of the p th atom and m the number of convolutions by which it is reached from the origin (reference point) with the help of $H_1(r)$. The probability distribution of the n th neighbour is

$$H_n(r) = 4\pi r^2 g(r) = \sum_p (H_p r) \dots (15)$$

The summation is to be taken over all the atoms belonging to the given n th neighbour. It is determined by the coordination number C_n . $\alpha^2/2 = \Delta^2 r$ denotes the mean square fluctuation of the first neighbour in any direction. It is evidently a measure of the dispersion of the distribution function.

It might be noted that neither $H_p(r)$ nor $H_n(r)$ are Gaussian functions and the properties of $H_n(r)$, i.e. of $g(r)$, are obtained from the convolution products of $H_1(r)$. This conclusively proves that the conventional method of analysis of RDF is neither mathematically nor physically correct, [cf. Figs. 13 (1-X) and 14 (1-X) of ref. 2].

For densely packed micro-clusters $g(r)$ function being the convolution product of the density function, would not differ significantly from that of a homogeneous structure of the "primitive" liquids. Consequently, it can be analysed with sufficient accuracy and reliability with the help of a single function $H_1(r)$. In practice, the values of α , C_n , r_n were determined with the help of least square method by fitting the theoretical curve with the given RDF throughout the region and not merely for a few humps of RDF (for details see ref. 3).

It should also be noted that the presence of clusters can be taken into consideration in this method by incorporating the distribution function $P_1(r)$ of the macro-lattice in which each of the clusters forms the building block of the macro-lattice.

It is interesting to note here that recently Baer¹² obtained an expression for $g(r)$ similar to (14) from considerations of "structural diffusion" of locally fluctuating lattice and using Fokker-Planck equation of stochastic processes. As critically discussed in ref. 6, locally fluctuating lattice as defined by Baer cannot produce an arbitrarily distorted lattice (generalised lattice) required for diffraction studies. Nevertheless, it is important to note that dynamic diffusion processes also give rise to neighbour statistics like eq. (14).

Continuous Small Angle Scattering

Small angle scattering has been used frequently to determine the "average size" of small particles by assuming that the most dominant part of it is due to the (000)-reflexion of the "particle". By studying the intensity function $I(b)$ of eq. (5) for $b \rightarrow 0$, one realises that other factors like density of packing, polydispersity, the background scattering due to lattice distortion of the second kind play their roles also in determining the nature of SAS. Much more detailed information can be obtained by analysing the Q-function properly. Since it is independent of any particular theory and can be directly obtained from the scattered intensity, it is perhaps the only satisfactory method available at present in the field of non-crystalline biological structures, catalysts and alloys. I had discussed⁴ the procedures for correctly deconvoluting the Q-function of such systems.

In applying this method to investigate the state of disorder of useful catalysts, it would be desirable at the beginning to study the shape, size and the degree of disorder from the Q-function by investigating systematically and quantitatively at different temperatures (from the room temperature to the

melting point) substances like aluminium and copper whose crystalline structures are well known. One should pay particular attention to the background scattering (usually neglected in all studies) to obtain the degree of disorder and distortion of the crystalline lattice quantitatively. It seems plausible that the effectiveness of a catalyst depends mainly on the fact that it had been reduced to distorted micro-crystallites in which the exposed sites contain loosely bound electrons capable of reacting easily with the other substances.

In the field of alloys the deconvolution of the Q-function can also offer useful information about their states of aggregation and can reconcile the present controversies regarding the nature of Guinier-Preston zones.

Summary

I should like to emphasize again that without taking into account the concepts and conclusions of the unified theory one would not be able to remove the ambiguities regarding the structural information obtained from conventional theories. Careful analysis of and application of this theory can yield many detailed and reliable structural parameters not possible to gather from the conventional theories. For many non-crystalline structures, the proper analysis of the Q-function remains the only viable method to obtain useful and reliable results.

The chart shown gives a birds-eye view of the connections between the Unified Theory and various other Kinematic theories.

References

1. R. HOSEMANN and S. N. BAGCHI, "Direct Analysis of Diffraction by Matter", North Holland, Amsterdam, 1962.
2. S. N. BAGCHI, *Advances in Physics*, 1970, 19, 119.
3. S. N. BAGCHI, *Acta Cryst.*, 1972, A28, 560.
4. S. N. BAGCHI, The Role of Q-function in Solving Biological Structures. Symposial Papers, International Biophysics Conference, Moscow, 1972, pp. 755-764.
5. S. N. BAGCHI and J. P. SUPPLE, *Phys. Chem. Liq.*, 1979, 8, 223.
6. S. N. BAGCHI and J. P. SUPPLE, *Phys. Chem. Liq.*, 1981, 11, 1.
7. S. N. BAGCHI, Unified Kinematic Theory of Diffraction and Disordered Structures. Abstract 22.2-01 of the Proceedings of XIIth International Congress of Crystallographers, Ottawa, 1981.
8. R. HOSEMANN and S. N. BAGCHI, *Acta Cryst.*, 1952, 5, 749.
9. R. HOSEMANN and S. N. BAGCHI, *Acta Cryst.*, 1953, 6, 318.
10. R. HOSEMANN and S. N. BAGCHI, *Acta Cryst.*, 1953, 6, 404.
11. R. HOSEMANN and S. N. BAGCHI, *Acta Cryst.*, 1954, 7, 237.
12. S. BAER, *Physica*, 1978, 91A, 603; *Chemical Physics (North Holland)*, 1979, 39, 159.